

Impact of Biochar Aging on Soil Physicochemical Properties

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Biochar undergoes significant transformations in soil as a result of chemical, physical, and biological processes. These alterations can impact its initial properties, influencing both its agronomic effectiveness and its capacity for carbon sequestration. Long-term observations of biochar aging effects in soil are limited but highly relevant, as they provide a more realistic picture of the agronomic and societal benefits of biochar than short-term studies with relatively “fresh” biochar. This study aimed to describe the aging effects of biochar and their impact on a range of soil properties at a long-term biochar experiment in Bayreuth, Germany. For this purpose, soil and biochar samples were taken 13 years after application (two variants: 1. co-composted and 2. pristine biochar) and compared with a fresh variant in which the same unaged biochar was freshly mixed with the control soil.

The soil quality parameters, pH and electrical conductivity, decreased significantly ($p < 0.05$) during biochar aging. Specifically, the pH dropped from 7.4 in freshly biochar-amended soil to 6.8 in the pristine aged biochar variant and 6.9 in the co-composted aged biochar variant. Electrical conductivity decreased from $217.0 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ in the freshly amended soil to $81.1 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ in the pristine aged variant and $87.6 \mu\text{S cm}^{-1}$ in the co-composted aged variant. Nitrogen retention was enhanced in the soil amended with co-composted aged biochar compared to the pristine aged biochar soil. Total nitrogen (TN) was higher at 1.94 g kg^{-1} versus 1.57 g kg^{-1} ($p < 0.05$), and ammonium-N ($\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$) was slightly elevated at 35.7 mg kg^{-1} versus 33.0 mg kg^{-1} , although the difference was not statistically significant. The nitrate-N ($\text{NO}_3^-\text{-N}$) content was significantly lower in all biochar-amended soil variants compared to the control soil. Total carbon (TC) levels decreased during biochar aging in all soil variants. However, the reduction was significantly lower in the co-composted aged biochar soil (25.0 g kg^{-1}) compared to the pristine aged biochar soil 20.5 g kg^{-1} , $p < 0.05$).

This study identified multiple aging effects on biochar following 13 years of exposure in loamy soil. Importantly, the results showed that compared to the amendment of pristine biochar, co-composting did not diminish TC of the treated soil, and more N could be retained, 13 years after amendment. In fact, co-composting prior to soil application is recommended to fully realize the potential agronomic benefits.

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